

Further Attempts to Prove Ternary Balanced Validity

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January 19, 2026

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Author's contributions

The sole author designed, analyzed, interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

Abstract

Aims/Objectives: Let me try to begin by comaring to graphs One of the function $f(x) = x(x - 2)(x - 1)$; Figure 1 Blue; and $f(x) = x(x - 1)(x + 1)$; Figure 1 Green. In essence the right one (blue) is the shift by one one unit along x-axis to the right of the green graph More specifically : $f(x) = x(x - 2)(x - 1) + 1 = f(x) = x(x - 1)(x + 1)$; Its graphically well-seen so the entire question of whether or not a Balanced set is valid should have been answered But how abot the applications? How can we apply this theory into practice? To answer this question let's turn to pure Algebra and Linear Maths These two will give us a clue on how continuous functions find their own applications in a digital world

1. General Information

The idea of the following research is to show how continuous functions can be represented in Linear Algebra The simplest way is to show that two vectors \hat{a} , and \hat{b} are linearly independent In that case linear combination of the two is not equal 0 when we add them Let's see if this is the case If

$A_i = D_i : |D_i = x(x-2)(x-1) \longrightarrow A_i = D_i + 1 \longrightarrow D_i + I$; If we consider graph represented by formula 2 to be of the type: $\binom{p}{3}$ then the 1st formula is corresponding linear representation of the graph in the form of $\binom{p}{3} + 1$

In that case the second formula becomes: $\frac{1}{3!} \left| \begin{matrix} p \\ p+1 \\ p-1 \end{matrix} \right|$ Whereas the

first one is: $\frac{1}{3!} \left| \begin{matrix} p \\ p-2 \\ p-1 \end{matrix} \right| \longrightarrow$

$$\frac{1}{3!} \Delta \left(\left| \begin{matrix} p \\ p-2 \\ p-1 \end{matrix} \right| + I \right) = \frac{1}{3!} \Delta \left(\left| \begin{matrix} p \\ p+1 \\ p-1 \end{matrix} \right| \right) \quad (1)$$

If you would consider any of the entries in Formula (1) to be the entries of a square $(n \times n)$ matrix or components of a vector then we would describe a entry under transformation: $\binom{p}{3} = \Delta D_i = \frac{i(i-1)(i-2)}{3!} \cdot I$:I is an Identity Matrix

2. Materials and Methods

Now what if we want our matrix entries to be equal some number $n \in Z$? In that instance we somehow have to adapt one system of counting to another Namely Ternary to Decimal We would also have to incorporate our number nto both The easiest way to do it would be in dealing with Series Here we talk about not just any series but converging and the point of convergence would be some universal unit let's make it equal 1 Now we place 1 into the right part of an equation and make it equal sum of entries: $\sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n-i}{2} a_i, b_i, c_i$ As such our formula looks like this:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n-i}{2} a_i, b_i, c_i = 1 \quad (2)$$

3. Methodology

We still have to specify a lot of data for the system to understand the principle of its work For instance,we don't know what the entries a_i, b_i, c_i

are. Well, those are the entries of our aforementioned diagonal matrix or to be more specific and accurate, the entries of its inverse. They are: $((n-i)(n-i-1)(n-i-2))^{-1}$. In other words: $a_i = \frac{1}{n-i}$; $b_i = \frac{1}{n-i-1}$; $c_i = \frac{1}{n-i-2}$. Depending on the number n : $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ a sought after matrix will have different number of entries (See Formula 2) and if we place those entries in three columns or, in other words, construct $p \times 3$ a Matrix then take its inverse and make the first row correspondent coordinates in a 3D Space then we will have $(x)(x-2)(x-1)$ and corresponding to it $\frac{1}{3}p(0, 2, 1)$ vector. Diagonal matrix will then have: $A - A' = I$ form

$$\begin{pmatrix} p & & \\ & p-1 & \\ & & p+1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} p-1 & & \\ & p-2 & \\ & & p \end{pmatrix} = I \quad (3)$$

Following this line of thinking if we now want to derive a general formula, we would have:

$$|A' - A| = I \longrightarrow |A| = \binom{p}{3} I \quad (4)$$

From the Formula (4) we can conclude that:

$$n |A' - A| = - \binom{p}{3} I \quad (5)$$

Finally cancelling the likes on the left and right in Formula (5), our final equation will look like this:

$$n = - \binom{p}{3} \quad (6)$$

where n is our input entry converts p into n and vice versa where both p and n are such that: $p, n \in \mathbb{Z}$

4 Results

We can extend our formula (4) further and state that

$$A' = D_i' \longrightarrow A' = \frac{1}{\binom{p}{3}} \quad (7)$$

Naturally it follows that, taking Formula (7) statement:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n a_i = \frac{1}{\binom{p}{3}} \quad (8)$$

Converting these into Ternary code or firstly converting it into integers is just a matter of choice:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} p \\ 3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

5 Conclusions

First and very important conclusion is that the sum of entries in Formula (9) is an integer or otherwise interpreted as:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n a_i = \begin{pmatrix} p \\ 3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Second, if we look at the formula (6) we can see that the entry $n := ?$ corresponds to a series with a negative sign, which can further be interpreted as an integer equivalent of a Diagonal Matrix multiplied by a three-component vector (x, y, z) results in an Eigenvalue multiplied by respective $-(ax, by, cz)$ vector which will have its application in engineering and field measurements. Question that has bothered me for a long time is how to find a correspondence between Balanced Ternary Set and the field of Real numbers $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ has been found though through a discussion with prof. Adrian Leonard Mociulschi and prof. Hussein Dakhil Al-Bahadli. I would like to present the updates on this discussion: The premise was that a set of Ternary numbers has its correspondence in Ternary. To prove that the Riemann sum of integers was taken: $\sum_{i=-n}^n i + 1 = S = \{x^2 : |x \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. However, this approach was not accurate enough as it gave us solutions for the set $\{0, 1\}$ instead of $\{-1, 0, 1\}$. The solution was found by adjusting a range and changes to the main formula.

$$2n \sum_{i=0}^{2n} i \rightarrow (x^2 - 1) x \quad (11)$$

It's a very general conclusion which needs further proof and explanation, but it brings us to the fact that Balanced Ternary set has its reflection in Cube numbers.

6 Figures and Graphs

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